

Birth Order as A Determinant of Self-Esteem, Psychological Flexibility And Emotional Intelligence

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Abstract: The study was conducted to study the influence of psychological flexibility, self-esteem, and emotional intelligence on birth order in young adults. In terms of research methodology, this was a quantitative, cause and effect survey design. This study recruited 510 Pakistanis young adults between the ages of 18 to 39 years, consisting of equal numbers of the first-born, middle-born, and last-born individuals (170 per group). Both males and females in equal number participated in this study. For this purpose, convenience and quota sampling methods were employed, along with the requirement of fluency in English. AAQ-II, Rosenberg Self-Esteem scale, and Schutte Self-report Emotional Intelligence Test (SSEIT) were used to collect data for analysis. No significant effect of birth order was found on personality variables. It was found that there is no significant effect on self-esteem, $F(2,507) = 0.806$, $p = 0.447$, $\eta^2 = 0.003$; psychological flexibility, $F(2,507) = 0.939$, $p = 0.392$, $\eta^2 = 0.004$; and emotional intelligence, $F(2,507) = 0.030$, $p = 0.971$, $\eta^2 = 0.000$. The study aimed to enhance understanding of birth order and its influence on personality characteristics.

Keywords: Psychological flexibility, Self-esteem, Emotional intelligence, birth order.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Birth order means the relative position of a person in the family in relation to his/her brothers and sisters. This concept is linked with the ideas of Alfred Adler, who claims that birth order determines personality formation in some way. Specifically, each member of the family has unique experiences related to their birth order in the family structure. Firstborn children are characterized as responsible, achievement-oriented, and leader-like. Middle-born children are

independent and peer-oriented. Last-born children tend to be sociable, attention-seeking, emotionally expressive, and adventure-seeking (Adler, 1927).

Birth order and personality remains a popular area of research in psychology for many years. Scientists have studied the impact of birth order on the intellectual development, creative abilities, academic achievements, interpersonal communication skills, and even mental well-being of individuals (Collins, 2006; Salmon, 2019). Sibling rivalry for parental attention and resources makes a significant contribution to personality development. As Sulloway (1999) states, firstborn children are provided with greater responsibility and parental expectations. Middle-born children tend to be deprived of parental care because of their low priority. Lastly, last-born children are pampered and protected by their parents and elder siblings, which influences their social and emotional development (Sulloway, 2007).

One of the personality factors that are related to the birth order is self-esteem. Self-esteem is defined as a person's evaluation of self-worth and self-acceptance (Rosenberg, 1965). It was noted that parental behaviours and family dynamics could influence self-esteem development. Adler postulated that successful adaptation in one's family role resulted in healthy self-esteem and self-concept formation (Eckstein et al., 2010). Research revealed that firstborns were more likely to display self-esteem compared to their siblings since they enjoyed more parents' attention and responsibilities (Falbo, 1981; Schwab & Laudgren, 1978). In contrast, the middle-born experienced low self-esteem because of exclusion feelings and lack of attention from parents (Kidwell, 1982). Parker and Benson (2004) argued that close relationships with parents positively affected self-esteem and emotional well-being during adolescence.

Another construct that relates to personality is psychological flexibility. Psychological flexibility can be described as being mindful of present experiences and accepting negative emotions and thoughts, as well as behaving based on the current context and personal values (Hayes et al., 1999). This concept allowed people to deal effectively with stress, problems, and difficulties that appeared to be challenging (Kashdan et al., 2006). Research found that higher psychological flexibility correlated with resilience, wellness, whereas psychological inflexibility is linked with anxiety, depression, and maladaptive coping patterns (Kashdan & Rottenberg, 2010; Gloster et al., 2017).

There is no consensus regarding research results related to birth order and psychological flexibility. In terms of Adlerian theory, firstborn children tend to be rigid and inflexible due to increased responsibilities and high expectations (Sulloway, 1999). In contrast, middleborn and youngest children have been observed to be more flexible as they learn how to adapt socially to the dynamics within families (Terzi, 2016). Nevertheless, Sharma & Srimathi (2014) state that firstborns possess more autonomy and self-sufficiency, along with better psychological well-being than later-born children. Therefore, further investigation is necessary concerning the connection between birth order and psychological flexibility in collectivistic societies, like that of Pakistan. Another crucial determinant of personality shaped by family experience and social interactions is emotional intelligence. It is defined as an individual's ability to recognize, comprehend, manage, and use their own and other people's emotions efficiently (Salovey & Mayer, 1991). According to Schutte, emotional intelligence includes the ability to perceive emotions, regulate emotions, empathize, and use emotions effectively (Schutte, 2020). The benefits associated with emotional intelligence include effective interpersonal relationships, academic achievement, professional performance, and improved mental health (Tagoe, 2016). A number of empirical studies have been carried out to investigate the relationship between birth order and emotional intelligence. Firstborn children are believed to be emotionally intelligent due to their leadership position and parental care role within the family (Vasavi, 2017). In comparison, younger siblings may acquire superior social intelligence and communication skills as a result of their dependency on social resources and social interaction

with elder siblings (Stefan, 2015). According to research findings obtained by Viegas (2014), there was a significant distinction between birth order and emotional intelligence among adolescents who lived with both parents. Likewise, Ahmad (2009) noted variations between gender and emotional intelligence.

Regarding Pakistan, little work has been done in studying the link between birth order and personality variables. According to Sultan (2020), Adlerian birth order theory was studied in Pakistani young adults, where first-borns were found to be resilient compared to their later-born counterparts who had higher levels of forgiveness. Likewise, Arshad (2006) noticed the correlation between birth order and psychological disorders including anxiety and depression in people suffering from conversion disorder. Nevertheless, it is important to mention that there is a huge gap in the literature on studying the effect of birth order on self-esteem, psychological flexibility, and emotional intelligence in Pakistani young adults.

Young adulthood is a crucial phase for personal development, during which individuals experience growth in terms of identity development, emotional maturity, autonomy, and sociability. Personality factors established during this phase play a major role in shaping an individual's future relationships, academic success, career performance, and psychological well-being.

The current study aims to examine psychological flexibility, self-esteem, and emotional intelligence as determinants of birth order among young adults in Pakistan. This study also seeks to evaluate the applicability of Adler's birth order theory in contemporary Pakistani society. The findings may contribute to the existing literature by providing empirical evidence regarding the relationship between birth order and personality characteristics. Furthermore, the study may help psychologists, educators, and researchers better understand how family structure influences personality development in young adults.

1.2 Problem Statement

The current study is focused on examining psychological flexibility, self-esteem, and emotional intelligence as predictors of birth order among young adults in Pakistan. The study is aimed at examining if first-born, middle-born, and last-born young adults show any difference in terms of self-esteem, psychological flexibility, and emotional intelligence.

1.3 Rational for the Study

Birth order continues to be one of the most controversial concepts in personality psychology. While there is much research done across countries exploring the link between birth order and personality traits, only a few studies have addressed these issues within Pakistan. In this regard, the current study would be very important since it would offer an empirical base for the validity of Adler's birth order theory in Pakistani culture. The results of the study would be helpful not only for further academic work but also for those practitioners who deal with the problem of personality development within families

1.4 Research Questions

- In what ways do birth orders (firstborns, middle children, and youngest children) influence personality traits in young adults?
- Does birth order have an impact on self-esteem among young adults?
- Does birth order have an impact on psychological flexibility among young adults?
- Does birth order have an impact on emotional intelligence among young adults?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

H1= Birth order has a significant impact on self-esteem among young adults.

H2= Birth order has a significant impact on psychological flexibility among young adults.

H3=Birth order has a significant impact on emotional intelligence among young adults.

2. Literature Review.

Birth Order has continued to be one of the most popular topics within personality psychology. The concept of birth order was first presented by Alfred Adler, who claimed that the birth order of a child plays a critical role in determining personality development, emotional adjustment, and behaviour patterns. As Adler (1927) asserts, all children go through a distinctive family situation depending on their birth order and, thus, form distinct attitudes, coping skills, and social behaviours. According to Adler, first-born children are likely to be ambitious, responsible, and good leaders since they enjoy constant parental care before the birth of siblings who result in making them feel "dethroned" in order to turn them into rigid, controlling, and perfectionists (Sulloway, 1999). On the other hand, middle children are regarded as independent, peer-oriented, and adaptable due to receiving comparatively less parental care and having to fight for parental attention. Lastly, youngest children are perceived as sociable, expressive, friendly, and attention seekers due to receiving comparatively more parental care (Adler, 1927).

The literature review reveals that there are many studies dedicated to examining the effects of birth order on personality characteristics, intelligence, interpersonal relationships, achievement, and psychopathology. Sulloway (1999). On the other hand, middle children are perceived as independent, peer-oriented, and adaptable due to receiving comparatively less parental care and fighting for parental attention. Lastly, youngest children are regarded as sociable, expressive, friendly, and attention seekers due to receiving comparatively more parental care (Adler, 1927). The role played by birth order in determining various factors such as personality characteristics, intelligence, relationships, academic performance, and psychological well-being has been examined widely by researchers. In his research, Sulloway (1999) found out that competition between siblings for the limited attention from their parents leads to personality differences between siblings. For instance, while first-born children exhibit greater conformity to social rules, later-born children are generally known to behave in a rebellious manner in order to carve out a niche in the family (Sulloway, 2007). In similar findings, Paulhus (1999) noted that firstborns are characterized by high levels of conscientiousness, dominance, and achievement, while later-born individuals are rebellious, extroverted, and open to experiences.

Among the important variables in relation to birth order are self-esteem levels. Self-esteem is described as one's overall judgment regarding the worth of the self (Rosenberg, 1965). In accordance with Adlerian psychology, birth order affects self-esteem since each sibling plays a specific position in the family leading to different levels of expectations from the parents. Resulting in different parental expectations, responsibilities, and emotional experiences (Eckstein et al., 2010). Research conducted by Falbo (1981) found that firstborn individuals generally possess higher self-esteem compared to later-born children, while middle-born females reported the lowest levels of self-esteem. Greater parental investment and parental responsibility are positively associated with self-concept in firstborn children, as suggested by the research. Similar results have been obtained by Schwab and Laudgren (1978), where the authors studied the impact of birth order on self-esteem among university students and found that firstborn individuals have high self-esteem levels compared to their later-born siblings, especially females. Furthermore, Schwab and Laudgren noted that both parental evaluations and societal acknowledgment influence the development of self-esteem.

Parental interactions and self-esteem were identified as important variables in the existing literature. For instance, Parker and Benson (2004) claimed that adolescents' self-esteem was positively correlated with their perception of parental closeness, warmth, and acceptance. Moreover, Kidwell (1982) stated that middle-born individuals tended to have low self-esteem levels and had issues with identity development since they felt that they received less attention from their parents than their siblings. Children who are recognized and supported by their parents tend to have adequate self-esteem and confidence, according to Brook (2010). Contradictory evidence has also been provided, for example, Romeo (1994) believed that

middle-born children could have higher self-esteem due to lack of parental expectations and responsibility.

Another research related to birth order that has been proposed as an explanation for the effects of birth order on personality development is psychological flexibility. Psychological flexibility is defined as the ability to stay present in the current situation despite uncomfortable feelings, ideas, or thoughts while adjusting one's behaviour to fit situations and personal value-based choices (Hayes et al., 1999). According to Kashdan and Rottenberg (2010), psychological flexibility can be understood as a person's ability to respond adequately to situational demands and maintain balance in the different aspects of his/her life. Psychological flexibility has been correlated with resilience, emotional well-being, mental well-being, and psychological health (Gloster et al., 2017). On the contrary, psychological inflexibility leads to anxiety, depression, rumination, and maladaptive behaviour (Kashdan & Rottenberg, 2010).

Research studies of the relationship between birth order and psychological flexibility have shown contradictory results. Within Adlerian theories, the firstborns tend to exhibit high levels of psychological inflexibility due to their parents' pressure and sense of duty (Sulloway, 1999). Middle or later-born children are psychologically more flexible as they adjust to changes in family situations (Terzi, 2016). Sultan (2020) investigated Adlerian birth order theory among Pakistani young adults and reported that firstborn individuals were more resilient than later-born children, whereas later-born individuals demonstrated greater forgiveness. Similarly, Sharma and Srimathi (2014) found that firstborn children displayed greater autonomy, self-acceptance, competence, and psychological wellbeing than later-born siblings. These contradictory findings indicate that the relationship between birth order and psychological flexibility remains unclear and may vary across cultural contexts.

The Acceptance and Action Questionnaire-II (AAQ-II) developed by Hayes et al. (1999) has frequently been used to assess psychological flexibility. Studies have shown that psychological flexibility contributes positively to quality of life, emotional wellbeing, and mental health functioning (Eilenberg et al., 2017; Forman et al., 2012). Kashdan and Rottenberg (2010) emphasized that psychological flexibility is not simply the absence of distress but rather the ability to adapt effectively despite experiencing difficult emotions and thoughts.

Another personality factor that can be linked to the birth order is emotional intelligence. According to Salovey & Mayer (1991), emotional intelligence can be described as the capacity of an individual to manage his/her emotions effectively through understanding, controlling, perceiving, and utilizing emotions. In the same breath, Schutte (2020) describes emotional intelligence as being characterized by emotional awareness, social skilfulness, emotional regulation, and empathy. Emotional intelligence has been positively correlated with academic excellence, interpersonal relations, occupational success, and overall psychological well-being (Tagoe, 2016).

The family environment and interactions between siblings contribute immensely to the development of emotional intelligence. The first-born children have usually been tasked with care taking and leadership roles in the family setting, hence contributing to emotional intelligence and responsibility (Vasavi, 2017). On the contrary, later born children tend to develop social and interpersonal intelligence since social interaction plays a crucial role (Stefan, 2015). Research carried out by Viegas (2014) among adolescents living with both parents has shown clear distinctions between birth order and emotional intelligence. Additionally, Kashan (2021) has established the positive correlation between birth order, emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and parental education of university students. Ahmad (2009) has equally revealed gender difference concerning emotional intelligence. Researchers have further investigated the impact of birth order on risky behaviours, academic success, and social adjustment. According to Fergusson et al. (2006), in their longitudinal study spanning over 25 years, first-born individuals displayed superior academic success than other birth order siblings. In addition to

this, Paulhus et al. (1999) indicated that first-born children showed greater responsibility, achievement motivation, and academic success than others. Nevertheless, those belonging to later-born groups were found to exhibit risk-taking behaviours such as substance use and impulsive acts (Argys et al., 2006; Zweigenhaft, 2000).

In Pakistan, studies about birth order and personality characteristics have remained limited. Arshad (2006) revealed a correlation between birth order, anxiety, depression, and conversion disorder. In a similar way, Sultan (2020) tested and validated the Adlerian Birth Order Theory in a Pakistani sample with respect to resilience and forgiveness. However, the impact of birth order on the self-esteem, psychological flexibility, and emotional intelligence of Pakistani young adults has not been studied empirically.

In conclusion, several studies have shown that birth order affects multiple aspects of personality development. However, discrepancies exist in the results obtained from various research studies because of cultural differences, family system variances, and methodology limitations. Therefore, the present study aims to further investigate psychological flexibility, self-esteem, and emotional intelligence as determinants of birth order among young adults in Pakistan.

3. Method

3.1 Research Design

The current study follows a quantitative cause and effect survey-based research design.

3.2 Participants

The target population selected for this study were young adults aged from 18 to 39 years (N=510). Which was divided equally into firstborn, middle-born, and last-born children (170 people in each category). Out of 170 people in each category 85 was male and another half would be female. The data was gathered from the Pakistani population. Convenience sampling was utilized to collect data and the quota sampling method were used.

3.3 Inclusion criteria:

- A sample of 255 young males and females each between the ages of 18 to 39 years were selected by quota sampling, which was collected from one public, one government, and one private university and different communities in Karachi.
- The participant has siblings (>2). The participants had a basic understanding of English. Participants were students of BS, MS/MPhil, Ph.D., and MBBS were taken as well as working professionals from different backgrounds, and non-working participants were also taken.
- Chronological birth orders of the participants were asked, thus we were able to take a sample of firstborn 170 (85 male and 85 female), second born 170 (85 male and 85 female), middleborn 170 (85 male and 85 female) which were from the lower, middle, and upper socioeconomic backgrounds
- Participants from both the nuclear and joint family systems were chosen.

3.4 Exclusion criteria:

- Participants who weren't included in this research were the one who was an only child. Participants who were (below age 18 or above age 39).
- The participants didn't have a basic understanding of English or didn't have any mental disorders.

3.5 Material:

3.5.1 Informed Consent: This included obtaining consent from the university under which research was conducted along with the consent of the authors of the test measures was attained. The participants of the research were also given a consent form in other to make sure their information is just utilized for the sake of research and their confidentiality is maintained. The participation of participants was entirely voluntary, and they can deny completing the study at any moment in time. Participants were aware of the purpose of our study.

3.5.2 Demographic Information Sheet: The demographic form includes information like; Age, Gender, Educational level, Family system, No. of siblings, Participant birth order (Firstborn, Middle born, Last born)

3.5.3 Rosenberg self-esteem scale

It was created in 1965 by, by Dr. Morris Rosenberg. This test was applied to measure the variable of self-esteem in young adults. The RSES is considered like the questionnaires based on a social survey. Half of the items are positive statements about one's self-esteem and another half are negative statements about one's self. It measures universal self-worth by assessing together the optimistic and destructive outlooks about the self. The novel model on which the scale was created contained 5, 024 high-school beginners along with elders from 10 indiscriminately a selection of schools in New York State. The Rosenberg self-esteem scale is considered a consistent and accurate measuring scale for self-esteem evaluation. The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale has high rankings in consistency areas. Its internal reliability was 0.77. A wide-ranging selection of samples such as a close relative, males older than 60, college pupils, and a member of civil service of independent studies exhibited alpha coefficients ranging from 0.72 to 0.87 which are all relatively elevated. A minimum range was considered at least 0.90 of the Coefficient of Reproducibility (Rosenberg, 1965). For the 2-week interval, the Test-retest consistency was calculated at 0.85, and the 7-month interval was calculated at 0.63 (Silber & Tippett, 1965, Shorkey & Whiteman, 1978). This scale is closely linked with the Coppersmith Self-Esteem Inventory.

3.5.4 The Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SSEIT)

It was developed by Nicola Schutte that is constructed based on the original model of emotional intelligence made by Salovey and Mayer (1990) recognized as the Schutte emotional intelligence scale or self-report emotional intelligence test to assess emotion on oneself and others. It can also assess the manifestation of emotion, regulation of emotion in the self and others, and presentation of emotion in problem-solving. This assessment tool includes 33 a self-report items inventory that is focused on emotional intelligence in which participants have to give ratings to themselves out of 5. To complete the test, participants need on average five minutes. The items are calculated by the reverse coding method. The higher the score signifies more emotional intelligence score. Over 200 publications have done citations of this scale which indicates its utilization in various studies to measure emotional intelligence which is listed in the PsycINFO database. The internal consistency of the evaluating emotions scale was identified through the measurement of Cronbach's alpha i.e., 0.90. The across samples mean is 0.87. The test-retest reliability of SSEIT is 0.78. For overall scale scores. The convergent validity of the scale is $r = 0.43$ which was substantially related to Assessment of Emotions Scale scores and the EQ-I. The across samples validity of the scale is correlated at 0.23 with results in several realms (Nicola S. Schutte N. B., 2009).

3.5.5 The acceptance and action questionnaire (AAQ-2)

The acceptance and action questionnaire were developed by Hayes and his associates in 2004, this 7-item questionnaire was made to assess the construct of experiential avoidance. It is used

to trace exactly how a person is doing regarding psychological flexibility skills in daily life on a weekly or biweekly basis. Simply add up the responses for each question to score it. A reduced amount of flexibility has considered when the scores on the scale come elevated, while more flexibility has considered when the scores come lesser. This second version of the Acceptance and Action Questionnaire (AAQ-II) can be explained by development and psychometric assessment through the current research which evaluates the construct referred to as, diversely, acceptance, experiential avoidance, and psychological inflexibility. The high reliability and validity of this measure can be specified through the outcomes of 2,816 participators across six samples. The AAQ-II scale has proven components of structure stability, internal consistency, test-retest consistency, convergent authenticity, predictive soundness, and discriminant rationality (Bond et al. 2011). The AAQ-II seems to measure a unidimensional factor across varied samples, consistent with the theory that suggests psychological inflexibility functions as a coherent construct. Moreover, as anticipated, the scale AAQ-II was linked with elevated levels of hopelessness, anxiety, nervousness, distress, depression overall psychological suffering. Correspondingly, the mean alpha coefficient is 0.84 (0.78-0.88), and the 3- and 12-month test-retest consistency is 0.81 and 0.79. A range of outcomes can be predicted and revealed through AAQ-II scores which are considered simultaneous, longitudinal, and incremental from mental health to work absence rates that are steady with its fundamental theory. Furthermore, it reveals suitable discriminant accuracy.

Like the AAQ-I, the AAQ-II measures the same concept. However, the AAQ-II scale has superior psychometric reliability.

3.6 Procedure

The permission was taken from the respective author of the scales that was used in the study. The entire questionnaire was comprising the following: Consent Form Demographic Information Form, and the scales namely. The scale of the Self-esteem scale by Rosenberg, the acceptance and action question (AAQ-2) by Clarissa W. Ong, Benjamin G, and the scale for self-report emotional intelligence by Schutte (SSEIT). All the contributors and participants of the study was taken from Pakistan between the age ranges of 18-39. Non- probability convenience sampling technique was used to gather data.

Firstly, participants were requested to sign the consent form afterward if they agree to participate in the study then we took another step. Like, such a demographic form (including information like age, gender, educational level, family system, number of siblings, etc.). It will take approximately 15-20 minutes to complete the questionnaire. At the end of the form, participants were shown thankfulness for their participation. After the data collection process, the data was entered into SPSS to carry out statistical analyses.

According to the American Psychological Association (APA) standard procedure, approval of authors to use the scales was obtained. The participants were provided with the consent forms before the survey was administered to them. Confidentiality was maintained; no participant was named, and any personal information of any participant shall not be revealed. Moreover, the questionnaire does not require respondents to enter their names, addresses, etc. Every participant will be given the right to withdraw, and they can drop out of the study at any point, without any consequences. Participants was protected to any harm in any way and respect for the dignity of the participant was prioritized. At the end of the administration, participants were expressed their gratitude for participating in our study.

Results.

The chapter presents a statistical analysis of results to investigate presence of significant relationship among the variables. Demographic variables of the participants have discussed along with descriptive analysis of participants. The information coded and analysed through statistical package for social sciences version 22.

4.1 Table No. 1

Demographic Variables of the Study Sample (N=510)

	<i>Categories</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>Age</i>	-	510	100.0	21.44	3.29
<i>Gender</i>	Male	255	50.0	1.50	0.50
	Female	255	50.0		
<i>Family Type</i>	Nuclear	408	80.0	1.20	0.40
	Joint	102	20.0		
<i>Birth Order</i>	First born	170	33.3	2.00	0.82
	Middle born	170	33.3		
	Last born	170	33.3		
<i>Number of Siblings</i>	1	25	4.9	3.50	1.46
	2	100	19.6		
	3	160	31.4		
	4	120	23.5		
	5	61	12.0		
	6	28	5.5		
	7	6	1.2		
	8	7	1.4		
	9	2	0.4		
	10	1	0.2		
	<i>Education</i>	Intermediate/A-Levels	44	8.6	2.33
Undergraduate		314	61.6		
Graduate		107	21.0		
Postgraduate		31	6.1		
Others		12	2.4		
<i>Occupation</i>	Student	408	80.0	1.31	0.71
	Professional	60	11.8		

Student Professional	& 33	6.5
Not Employed	7	1.4
Other	2	0.4

Note: *N* = Total Participants, *M* = Mean, *SD* = Standard Deviation, *f* = frequency, % = Percentage.

Table 1 mentioned above indicates the Frequency, Percentage, mean, and standard deviation of the demographic variables that were considered in the current study. The age range falls from 18 to 39 year.

4.2 Table 2

Descriptive Statistics for Rosenberg self-esteem scale, The Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SSEIT), the acceptance and action questionnaire (AAQ-2) (N= 510)

Measures	item	α	M	SD	Min	Max	Sk
Rosenberg self-esteem scale	10	0.781	18.9373	4.65678	0.00	30.00	-
The Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test	33	0.885	117.8059	16.59738	55.00	155.00	-
The acceptance and action questionnaire	7	0.848	25.1549	9.65788	7.00	49.00	0.221 -0.642

Note: α = cronbach’s alpha, *M* = Mean, *SD* = Standard Deviation, *SK* = Skewness, *K* = Kurtosis.

Table 2 shows descriptive statistics and cronbach’s alpha of all the variables. Data reveals that all the scales have good reliability of $\alpha = 0.7$ to $\alpha = 0.9$ which indicates acceptable to excellent range and internal consistency. Furthermore, the other factors that are included in the descriptive statistics are mean and standard deviation. Normal distribution of information is represented by values of skewness and kurtosis. According to the criteria as given by George and Mallery (2010), Gravetter and Wallunau (2014), values of skewness and kurtosis must lie between +2 and -2 to consider that the data is normally distributed and all the values are under this range, therefore parametric tests are used in this study.

4.3 Table 3

One Way Anova for Effects of Birth Order on Self Esteem, psychological flexibility, and

emotional intelligence.

Measure	First Born		Second Born		Third Born		F (2, 507)
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	
Self Esteem	19.252	4.696	18.947	4.686	18.611	4.591	0.806
	0.003						0.447
Psychological flexibility		24.44	9.14	25.88	9.85	25.13	9.95
	0.004						0.93
Emotional intelligence	117.7	18.64	117.65	15.54	118.05	15.50	0.030
	0.000						0.971

Table 5 shows results of one-way anova. Results specifies that there is no significant effect of birth order on self-esteem, $F(2,507) = 0.806, p = 0.447, \eta^2 = 0.003$. Secondly it also shows that there is no significant relationship between birth order on psychological flexibility, $F(2,507) = 0.939, p = 0.392, \eta^2 = 0.004$. Lastly, the results also suggests that there is no significant effect of birth order on emotional intelligence, $F(2,507) = 0.030, p = 0.971, \eta^2 = 0.000$

4.4 Table 4

Post Hoc analysis for Effects of Birth Order on Self Esteem, psychological flexibility, and emotional intelligence.

Dependent Variable	(I) birth order	(J) birth orders	MD (I-J)	Sig.	95% CI	
					LB	UB
Self- esteem	First born	Middle born	0.3059	0.817	-0.8819	1.4936
		Last born	0.6412	0.413	-0.5466	1.8289
	Middle born	First born	-0.3059	0.817	-1.4936	0.8819
		Last born	0.3353	0.785	-0.8525	1.5230
	Last born	First born	-0.6412	0.413	-1.8289	0.5466
		Middle born	-0.3353	0.785	-1.5230	0.8525
Psychologica l flexibility	First born	Middle born	-1.4353	0.357	-3.8980	1.0274
		Last born	-0.6882	0.789	-3.1509	1.7744
	Middle born	First born	1.4353	0.357	-1.0274	3.8980
		Last born	0.7471	0.756	-1.7156	3.2097
	Last born	First born	0.6882	0.789	-1.7744	3.1509

		Middle born	-0.7471	0.756	-3.2097	1.7156
Emotional intelligence	First born	Middle born	0.0412	1.000	-4.1986	4.2809
		Last born	-0.3588	0.978	-4.5986	3.8809
	Middle born	First born	-0.0412	1.000	-4.2809	4.1986
		Last born	-0.4000	0.973	-4.6398	3.8398
	Last born	First born	0.3588	0.978	-3.8809	4.5986
		Middle born	0.4000	0.973	-3.8398	4.6398

***Significant difference (mean significance is different at the 0.05 level)**

The above table reveals that there is no significant effect of birth order on self-esteem of first born and middle born (.817) also there is no significant effect on self-esteem of first born and last born (.413) and there is also no significant effect on self-esteem of middle born and last born (.785).

There is no significant effect on psychological flexibility of first born and middle born (.357) also there is no effect on psychological flexibility of first born and last born (.789) and there is no effect on psychological flexibility of middle born and last born (.756)

Also, there is no significant effect on emotional intelligence of first born and middle born (1.00) also there is no effect on emotional intelligence of first born and last born (.978) and there is no effect on emotional intelligence of middle born and last born (.973)

4. DISCUSSION

Research intend to examine the effect of birth order (firstborn, middleborn, thirdborn) on psychological flexibility, self-esteem, and emotional intelligence among young adults. The information was gathered through quantitative cause and effect survey-based design (Male n=255, Female n=255) to prevent biasness and maintain generalizability. The sample comprised 510, both males and females 85 in each category. It was directed to explore the relationship of personality factors (psychological flexibility, self-esteem, and emotional intelligence) with birth order among young adults.

The first hypothesis of the study is that “there will be an effect of birth order on self- esteem” however findings did not support the hypothesis. The study findings contradict the prior studies that show a relationship between birth orders and self-esteem. According to the prior studies, Falbo (1981) proposed that ordinal birth position can affects self-esteem in young adults and adolescents. Results revealed that the firstborn tended to have high self-esteem than the last born, and lower self-esteem was presented in middle-born women. (Fablo, 1981). Birth order can also be related to how the individual is understood, seen, and perceived by others (Schwab &Laudgren, 1978). Several research has shown that the connection between parents and children is one of the greatest important signs to specify the self-esteem of a person (Parker & Benson, 2004). Kidwell's (1982) findings indicate that child self-esteem is a result of parents' reflective assessment of a child's innate worth that appears through a child-parent interface. (Kidwell, 1982). Hence, if the interface between parents and children is the same among all siblings, the outcome ought to represent an equivalent amount of self-esteem between all siblings.

The second hypothesis of the study was that “there will be an effect of birth order on psychological flexibility” the findings did not aid our hypothesis. Statistical findings of the result indicate there is no significant relationship between birth order on psychological flexibility ($p=0.392$). Our findings contradict the previous findings as Adler said certain personality types are more likely than others to regain physical and psychological health through adaptive behaviours.

Middle and last-born siblings were shown to be more psychologically flexible than the firstborn in terms of social interest, active planning, acceptance, cognitive restructuring, as well as seeking external support. However, what Sharma and Srimanthi (2014) found in their study was that children who were first born had better anatomy, environmental mastery, individual own progress, optimistic associations, determination in life, and self-acceptance than middle children, suggesting flexibility is more important in first-borns than in last-born. Another study suggests greater flexibility in first and second-born than in last-born. (Yager, 2014).

The study's third hypothesis states that “There is an effect of birth order (firstborn, middle born & last born) on emotional intelligence” findings didn't support our hypothesis. The findings of the study find contradict the prior studies that show a relationship between birth order and emotional intelligence. Our findings contradict the previous studies as according to Vasavi, the firstborn has higher emotional intelligence. Also, there were limited studies that shows a connection between birth order and emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence can be measured in terms of job satisfaction (Tagoe, 2016) and development of self-regulation, and control of disruptive behaviours by considering the feelings and emotions of others (Dangmei, 2017) but there is no relationship with birth order.

Results of the findings shows, there is no discernible relationship between birth order and self-esteem ($F(2,507) = 0.806$, $p = 0.447$, $\eta^2 = 0.003$). Second, it demonstrates that there is no relationship between psychological flexibility and birth order, with $F(2,507) = 0.939$, $p = 0.392$, and $\eta^2 = 0.004$. Finally, the findings show that birth order has no discernible influence on emotional intelligence, with $F(2,507) = 0.030$, $p = 0.971$, and $\eta^2 = 0.000$. Statistical analysis, such as a one-way ANOVA, was used to explore the data. The purpose of the study was to determine how birth order affects the personality characteristics of self-esteem, psychological flexibility, and emotional intelligence. A systematic self-report questionnaire intended to investigate the relationship between personality characteristics such as self-esteem, psychological adaptability, emotional intelligence, and birth order.

5. Limitations and suggestions

- This research is that siblings of the same family were not taken to signify birth order changes because most of the respondents were having either sibling above 39 years or younger siblings below 18yrs. In a situation like this gathered information could be ambiguous, which leads to incompatible outcomes.
- Single children were not sampled due to the less availability of such samples. The researcher can conduct research on birth order by taking different variables from our study to see if it has a different outcome in our culture and society. However, research can also be conducted on the same topic and taking the same variables by changing sampling techniques and methods.
- future researches can be carried out by taking interviews with participants and so on. Additionally, in future studies, different data questionnaires can also help to validate the

outcome. This study also provides the guideline for future research with a wide clinical, educational, and organizational perspective.

6. Implications of the study.

- Clinicians can utilize these conclusions to know how birth order is linked to the personality of young adults. Also, these findings can be used to get a better understanding of how birth order is related to self-esteem, flexibility, and emotional intelligence.
- The information can be used to develop the different types of techniques that will help young adults with low self-esteem and help them to adapt to the environment flexibly with the understanding of emotions.
- The research will provide insight and an improved understanding of the concept of birth order and how it affects personality characteristics.
- The research will also help individuals to know how birth order affects parent-child and sibling relationships
- No apparent research was observed on the variables of birth order, personality, self-esteem, psychological flexibility, and emotional intelligence in young adults.
- Research will fill a gap in the academic literature and methodological strength of this study is the high internal consistency of the three scales used. All three scales did reliably consistent measurements. Consequently, the usage of these measures fortifies the accuracy and educational values of the current study.

7. Conclusion

This research was directed to evaluate the influence of a person's birth ordinal position on several personality characteristics of young adults. To investigate the data a statistical analysis i.e., one-way ANOVA was applied. Consequently, the application of a single factor. The study aimed to find out the impact of birth order on personality characteristics, i.e. self-esteem, psychological flexibility, and emotional intelligence. A structured self-report questionnaire was used to examine and probe the impact of birth order on personality characteristics i.e., self-esteem, psychological flexibility, and emotional intelligence. The results point out that there is no significant effect of birth order on self-esteem, $F(2,507) = 0.806$, $p = 0.447$, $\eta^2 = 0.003$. Secondly it also shows that there is no significant relationship between birth order on psychological flexibility, $F(2,507) = 0.939$, $p = 0.392$, $\eta^2 = 0.004$. Finally, the results also indicate that there is no significant effect of birth order on emotional intelligence, $F(2,507) = 0.030$, $p = 0.971$, $\eta^2 = 0.000$. In the end, we concluded that this study did not support the impact of birth order on personality formation in young adults and we also concluded that current research does not support the Adlerian theory in Pakistani culture. We invite researchers to empirically review and observe new emerging trends in the field of personality.

8. References

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